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Federal University Lokoja**

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Editorial Preface

It is with a great sense of commitment to scholarship that I present **LOJEL: Lokoja Journal of English & Literature**, Volume 2, 2025, a publication of the Department of English & Literary Studies, Faculty of Arts, Federal University Lokoja. We regret our inability to publish since our maiden volume 1, No.2. Now that we have bounced back again, we promise to keep up the tempo of consistency in publication.

This Volume has come out with a luscious harvest of fifteen (15) scholarly essays that have passed through stringent scrutiny with the sole aim of keeping faith with sustaining a quality journal that will stand the test of time. With a bumper harvest of fifteen articles that cut across diverse areas of English Language and Literature with different approaches to the interpretation, interrogation and analyses of its epistemology, I present this journal to the reading public.

I thank the Editorial Advisers, the Editorial Board, contributors and staff of the department for their steadfastness and support in making this dream a reality. We hope and pray to keep the journal afloat always even in these austere times.

If, in the course of reading, any errors are detected, it is highly regretted.

Happy Reading!

Prof. Ayodele Bamidele,

Editor

LOKOJA JOURNAL OF ENGLISH AND LITERATURE (LOJEL)

DEPARTMENT OF ENGLISH AND LITERARY STUDIES
FEDERAL UNIVERSITY LOKOJA

CALL FOR PAPERS
* LANGUAGE * LITERATURE * LINGUISTICS

Lokoja Journal of English and Literature (LOJEL) is a journal of the Department of English and Literary Studies, Federal University Lokoja. The journal is totally committed to the advancement of research in language and literary studies. The journal publishes well-researched papers in language, literature and linguistics. It is online, domiciled and hosted on the website of Federal University Lokoja, and in print. The Editorial Board hereby calls for manuscripts on the areas already mentioned for this volume of the journal.

GUIDELINES TO CONTRIBUTORS

- ❖ Authors should indicate their full names, institutional affiliations, phone numbers and emails on the cover page of their submissions.
- ❖ Manuscripts should be preceded by the title and an abstract of not more than 200 words.
- ❖ Manuscripts should not exceed 15 pages of A4 sized paper including references.
- ❖ Manuscripts should be typed with Microsoft Word, typed in Times New Roman with font size 12, double line spacing and submitted as email attachment.
- ❖ All papers sent to LOJEL must not have been submitted for assessment or published elsewhere.
- ❖ Authors are to maintain originality as they are responsible for the information, facts and opinions contained in their various papers.
- ❖ As a rule, all articles will be subjected to constructive criticism/peer reviews and editing, prior to acceptance and publication.
- ❖ Manuscripts should conform to the latest American Psychological Association (APA) format for language-based articles and Modern Language Association (MLA) for literature-based articles.

ASSESSMENT AND PUBLICATION FEES

- ❖ All manuscripts and correspondences should be sent electronically to lojel2020@gmail.com.
- ❖ Assessment fee - **₦10,000** (paid on submission of manuscript. Submit/attach evidence of payment alongside manuscript).
- ❖ Publication fee - **₦30,000** (paid upon acceptance of manuscript).
- ACCOUNT NAME: Lokoja Journal of English and Literature**
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- ❖ Two or more authors are entitled to only one copy of the journal. More copies can be purchased on request by any contributor at the cost of **₦5000** each.
- ❖ Submission for this volume is till **30th August, 2026** Any submission after the said date will be rescheduled for the next volume.

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